

Quiz 2 Algorithmic Thinking (JAVA)

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NAME: _____

[2p] Question 1.

a) Imagine a grandmother who will only approve you dating her grandchild if you are older than 18 **and** younger than 30, **and** either rich or really good looking. Assume that *age*, *income* and *cuteness* are variables describing these properties. *Age* and *income* are both integer variables, and *cuteness* contains a double. Rich means that your *income* should be over 50000, and 'really good looking' means that your *cuteness* should score at least 8.5 points (out of 10).

Draw a flowchart for an algorithm that prints "permission granted" if all requirements are met, and prints "rejected" if not.

[1p] Bonus: Make a flowchart that contains **at most one** decision diamond.

[3p] Question 2.

a) Trace the variables **a** and **b** in the flowchart below. Use a table to keep track of each variable's value after executing each statement.

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b) Think about the purpose or outcome of the algorithm specified by the flowchart above. Determine a meaningful name for the method:

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[5p] Question 3.

Dodo is standing in front of a row of eggs (facing towards them), as shown in the figure below:

Each egg has a certain value (a positive integer), and these values may be different. Dodo's task is to figure out which egg is the most valuable. Dodo must follow the sequence eggs, remembering **both the position and value** of the most valuable egg. At the end of the sequence Dodo should print these values in the console (using `System.out.println`).

You may assume that Dodo is initially on top of the first egg of the sequence. Since all eggs are lying in the same row, it is sufficient to only keep track of the column (or cell) in which the egg appears.

Write a program which prints the value and position of the most valuable egg in the console.

Hint: If Dodo is on top of an egg, she can obtain the value of that egg by using the method `public int getEggValue()`. The x-coordinate of the egg can be attained using the method `public int getEggX()`.

[7p] Question 4.

Suppose we have the following method **jump** which makes Dodo repeatedly take steps until she cannot move any further (either a fence is blocking her path or she has reached the end of the world):

```
public void jump() {  
    while ( ! borderAhead() && ! fenceAhead() ){  
        step();  
    }  
}
```

We call this method in the **act** as follows:

```
public void act() {  
    if ( foundEgg() ) {  
        Greenfoot.stop();  
    } else {  
        turnRight();  
        jump();  
    }  
}
```

The scenario is executed by pressing the **run** button. Hence, **act** is continuously repeated until **Greenfoot.stop()** has been called. The figure below shows three different initial configurations.

a) Does the program stop for configuration **A**? If so, how often was the **jump** method called?

b) Does the program stop for configuration **B**? If so, how often was the `jump` method called?

Suppose we want to Dodo to find the egg in configuration **C**. We can do this by placing fences in the world, at carefully selected locations. However, it **not** allowed to place any fence immediately next to the border.

c) Place the fences in the figure below such that you need no more than 5 fences for Dodo to find the egg after the *run* has been pressed.

